

Gezi - 10 Years After, Maxim Gorki Theatre, 26 May - 25 June, 2023

Gezinema World Cinema Documentaries

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Co-curated by Şirin Fulya Erensoy and Necati Sönmez

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Screening: Beirut: Eye of the Storm, Mai Masri, 2021

Four young women in Beirut document a turbulent period in recent Lebanese history, from the uprising against the ruling regime to the subsequent lockdown and then, just months later, the gigantic explosion at the port.

Q&A Session with Noel Keserwany, moderated by Şirin Fulya Erensoy and Necati Sönmez

Noel Keserwany is a multidisciplinary artist from Lebanon. Growing up amidst socio-political turmoil in Lebanon, she developed a vocal criticism of the situation using different storytelling methods. Since 2012, Noel and her sister Michelle have been writing and directing music videos to denounce the corrupt Lebanese political system. Their latest work, the short film "Les Chenilles," won the Golden Bear for Short Film at the 2023 Berlin Film Festival (Berlinale) and the Jury Prize at the Arab Film Festival in Malmo. It is currently in competition at several international festivals. Noel is currently developing "Seven Mountains and Seven Seas," an animated short film based on a story by Lebanese writer Emily Nasrallah, which received funding from the DFI for development. Additionally, she is working on her fiction film "Un An." Together with Michelle Keserwany, she is also developing their political documentary "à feu doux.

ŞE: Hello everyone. We are with Noel Keswany, thank you for being with us today.

NK: Thank you very much for having us and thank you for staying on a Sunday night...

ŞE: This is a very heavy film. I do not know if it is just me feeling the extra weight of this tonight. This is our third screening in the context of the GeZinema program and we have been watching films on Gezi these past two days and so a lot of our discussions have been around what has happened in the last 10 years, how we have dealt with ups and downs, the political developments and how that has shaped our resistance and forms of struggle both in Turkey and in the diaspora here. This is also a very beautiful film that looks and longs, and wishes for alternatives in a very turbulent country with a very complicated past and with many

generational differences in terms of how to move forward and to create change. There is the euphoria of the revolution which is disrupted by the coronavirus, the pandemic, and the most devastating explosion that brought to the forefront the horrible corruption that is part of the system. That was in 2019-20. I would just like to know how you feel about these events watching them now 4 years on.

NK: I cannot see it as a film. I see it as a start of something that is still continuing. The situation in Lebanon now is ten times worse and the downfall is very fast, and there is no horizon, there is nothing that is being done by the government to prevent further damage so the situation is getting worse and there is no horizon. It is not like you can really analyse any further than what is happening day by day which is a very fast time force. I do not want to say how I feel about this because I think I need to express it in another way and words do not do justice.

NS: Let's talk about how this started. There is a background. We know what happened after is probably another sad story. We know that there were a series of resistance movements on the street starting with the garbage crisis, can you speak about what the motivation was for people to go on the street?

NK: This is a great history lesson, but unfortunately, we don't have time to go into all the details. The 17th of October Uprising began after 30 years of corruption (and 15 years of civil war before this), and everyone felt that things were going terribly wrong. Housing and rent were unaffordable, jobs were scarce, and the same political system had been in power for those 30 years. Corruption was rampant, slowly killing the citizens. However, on October 17th, 2019, the situation escalated dramatically. The banking crisis hit another level, and people realised that they were losing all the money they had worked for throughout their lives, as the banks stopped giving money to the public. It's essential to recognize

that the issues in Lebanon go beyond just the banking system. Many Lebanese people don't even have bank accounts and are suffering from hunger today. The explosion of frustration on October 17th was a culmination of 30 years of oppression, primarily economic. The political system clung to power through corruption, fear and clientelism, with leaders acting like enemies on TV but forming coalitions during elections to maintain their reign. Unfortunately, there was no economic plan in those 30 years, leading the country to break down completely.

ŞE: In the film there is a highlight on how there is a lot of difference in terms of how each generation responds to political dissatisfaction. So your parents' generation who obviously underwent the civil war have a different approach to social change. You talk about in the film: you mention that they would rather remain silent than disrupt the unsteady balance of political power and yet, your generation is very different, you are out on the streets and you do not want to stay silent in the face of all this and this non-functioning system, and yet we see your mother in the film who is supportive and following your acts on the street. Can you maybe speak about the generational differences, how you use that to build upon it and to continue your resistance, and how that has created obstacles in creating a collective political action?

NK: I believe we can learn a lot from our parents' generation. They belong to the older generation that brought us to where we are now, and we, the current generation, have the responsibility to take this further. Looking back, I understand that during their time, they had limited options, with the war in Lebanon threatening lives and families. If I were in their shoes, facing the possibility of my sister being killed, I cannot predict how I would have acted. It is reasonable to assume that they made choices based on what they knew and the circumstances they faced at the time. After the war, many individuals from our parents' generation shifted their positions when they witnessed the changes in political parties' discourse after numerous people had died. Some were able to reject the political parties, while others couldn't, due to the legitimate trauma caused by the war. I dislike blaming this generation entirely, as trauma has a profound impact on people. The 15 years of war left lasting scars that are not easily healed. I was born in 1990, just after the war, which meant I didn't directly experience it. However, in 2015, we faced the garbage crisis with streets filled with mountains of garbage, and our generation endured nine years without elections, paying taxes and bearing the consequences of a system we didn't vote for. In 2018, we finally had our first elections: the first for our generation, not the whole country indeed. After 9 years of unconstitutional delay of elections we finally had the chance to vote. Then, in 2019, the situation escalated further. It feels like a continuation of events that began a long time ago, with each significant chapter building upon the other. The process is slow and often obscured by chaos and crises, making it challenging to perceive the changes that are occurring. In response to your

question, I believe we can learn valuable lessons from our parents' generation, even though they carry traumas from the past. I am glad to witness some individuals from our parents' generation changing their political position despite the difficulties they have faced.

ŞE: Does the audience have any questions?

Q: Thank you for your film. One of the things that I took away from your film was this tension between observation and participation, maybe especially for those who are behind the camera. I was wondering if you could speak a little bit about that? When you are there you are making this movie to share with people who are not there. How do you deal with that, staying present but also making sure that the observations are there for people who are not present?

NK: Do you mean when Mai was filming? Mai is the director of the film, when she was filming us, you mean how we felt? Or how we felt during our music videos when we made them?

Q: Yes, both of those questions.

NK: We agreed to be part of Mai's film because we were aware of how politicised television works in Lebanon. Each TV channel is directly linked to a political party, which means true representation is almost impossible. You are never truly represented. Our aim was to show this reality, as we felt it was crucial to be represented properly. It wasn't a mere option; it felt like a way to ensure our voices were heard. Moreover, Mai's extensive experience in filmmaking, particularly her past work documenting Lebanon and Palestine, earned our respect and trust. She is a pioneer in documentaries in the region, which further solidified our confidence in her as a filmmaker. Trust was a crucial aspect of our decision, and we felt we could rely on her to handle the project with integrity. During the year we spent with Mai, we developed a strong bond and relationship of trust. Much of the time we spent together was not dedicated to filming, and Mai was skilled at making us feel comfortable and unintrusive during the process. We didn't sense a constant presence of cameras around us. When it came to the music videos, we felt compelled to take action, as it was something we knew well and felt confident in doing. For us, it was the most natural way to contribute, just as others were cooking or providing sandwiches based on their abilities. This shared sense of using our skills to help made us feel that documenting through filming was the right thing to do.

ŞE: Speaking of the music videos, you said you started 10 years ago, was there a specific thing that had happened, that was a turning point for you to turn to this creative outlet and how has the response been? Sometimes there is a fine line between humour and serious political critique so for you, what does it mean to use humour to bring attention to political issues that general audiences would perhaps otherwise overlook or maybe not understand?

NK: Ten years ago, the first thing we did was the song "3al Jamal Bi wassat Beirut/On Camels in Downtown Beirut." I was 21, and Michel was 23, and we sensed that something was wrong. It's evident when you walk Downtown and talk to older people; you can feel the depression lingering, even though nobody openly discusses it. People can barely afford anything, but they still want to project an image of having a nice house, car, and a successful life. This disconnect between reality and appearances was frustrating for us. We felt the need to escape from this environment and release our pent-up frustration. Back then, we didn't know exactly where we were headed. Even in our earlier songs, which we played with our friends, the lyrics were not fully translated; we were merely expressing our emotions and trying to cope. Surprisingly, when we uploaded "3al Jamal Bi wassat Beirut/On Camels in Downtown Beirut." online, it quickly went viral, and we saw people singing it just a few days later. This encouraged us to channel our frustration into more structured music, and we realised that we could continue doing this. Initially, neither of us had plans to pursue careers in filmmaking or music. I thought I would focus on painting and illustration, while Michelle considered cartoons or comics. However, as the situation in the country grew harsher, and our frustration escalated, we decided to form a film crew that grew alongside us. This was how we learned filmmaking and continued with it, mainly driven by the challenging political situation in Lebanon.

NS: How do you feel as a generation, your generation... We have seen it in other films and countries, and the dilemma of whether to stay or leave... You left already, you are in France now. How do you think your generation is feeling now in your country?

NK: I was in Beirut just a few weeks ago, staying there for 2 months. Trying to strike a balance between both countries, France and Lebanon, is challenging when you constantly change locations. However, finding that equilibrium is essential to feel more settled and content.

Being in Beirut, I felt connected to Lebanon as a whole, not just the capital city. It was striking to observe that a significant majority, around 90% of my friends, were on antidepressants, which was not the case before. While being on antidepressants is not a problem in itself, the prevalence of depression reaching such levels surprised me. Despite being in touch with my friends and keeping up with news, witnessing the reality in person is different. The atmosphere in Lebanon is extremely depressing, with no apparent positive outlook. Many of my friends have had to accept low-paying jobs for about 300 USD/month, which is barely enough to cover basic expenses, especially considering the high costs of imported products. The reliance on imports has made everything in the supermarkets very expensive, leaving people with no hope for improvement or a better future. Both those who have left Lebanon and those who have stayed seem to be struggling to find their balance, as the situation's downward spiral shows no signs of stopping. It's challenging to express the extent of the hardship.

Q: May I ask, what was the reaction to the song that you performed in the beginning of the protests? We are quite used to this in Turkey where women are under threat on a daily basis. They are targeted everywhere, in the public and private sphere, as well as online. I was wondering if there had been any personal defamation especially considering that you might come from a conservative background or family... If it is not personal, I am asking.

NK: Do you mean whether there were threats?

Q: Threats... Any comments, people missing the point and humour of the song.

NK: Of course, we always receive negative comments. Surprisingly, we haven't received any direct threats yet, which is interesting because many of our friends who do stand-up comedy and similar things often face big threats and even physical attacks in the streets. However, we do encounter a lot of hate from people who strongly disagree with our political stance, and that's alright. When you are expressing political views, it's natural that some people won't like it, especially those who are affiliated with the traditional old political parties. The ones who support the current political system tend to dislike us, while those who seek change and reform in the political system are our biggest supporters, collaborators and friends. At one point, one of our songs, "ka2an 3ayshin / As if we were living" was flagged, coinciding with a time when the oppression from political parties increased. They were using bots on the internet to silence anything that opposed them. Fortunately, we contacted YouTube, explained the situation politely, and they restored the song. So, in the end, everything turned out fine.

NS: ... We were speaking this morning and you said you were working on a documentary... Which is about a long history which you are now enduring. Can you tell us a bit about this?

NK:

It's called "à feux doux /Sizzling Fire" Michelle and I are collaborating on a feature documentary that delves into the past 30 years of Lebanon. The current situation in Lebanon is incredibly complex, and we feel that it can't be adequately expressed solely through music videos. While we will continue making music videos, we also needed to create something more extensive and in-depth, a documentary that allows us the space and time to explore the subject thoroughly. This format offers a different approach to our work and allows us to delve into the complexities of the issues we want to address.

NS: We look forward to seeing it.

Q: I was wondering about the Palestinians. Did they join you? I saw someone waving the flag.

NK: Yes, a lot of Palestinians joined us. A lot of people who are with the Palestinian cause were on the streets and a lot of minorities found their places in this uprising. The minorities were in the uprising a lot and part of the supporters of the Palestinian cause.

NS: By the way the filmmaker Mai Masri is Palestinian. We forgot to mention that Mai is one of the most important Palestinian filmmakers.

NK: That is true, Mai is one of the pioneers of Palestinian film.

ŞE: I know you mentioned trying to maintain a balance between Beirut and Paris, or France and Lebanon, in terms of your living arrangements and connections. Since you have been in France, what kind of encounters have you had with the Lebanese diaspora? After or during the civil war, many people left Lebanon, leading to the establishment of diaspora communities. Additionally, a lot of people from your generation may also be seeking ways to leave the country. For instance, in Turkish diasporas, there can be prejudices and polarizations that are often influenced by governments. However, through open discussions, empathy can be formed, leading to a better understanding of one another. Is there a similar situation for the Lebanese, and how has your experience been in France?

NK:I have been in Paris for 2 years, and I haven't had the opportunity to meet the entire Lebanese diaspora as I don't go out much. One thing that stands out is that after 2019, another social class joined the diaspora. Better not put this first part, is it looks like a fact while there are no numbers and facts. In 2019, many people, including myself and my friends, felt compelled to leave due to the lack of prospects and opportunities in Lebanon. This led to a different dynamic in the diaspora. I have encountered both the older, more established diaspora and the new arrivals who have recently left Lebanon. It's interesting to observe the differences between them. The older diaspora seems to be more well-established and balanced, whereas the newer arrivals are still finding their footing and balance in their new environment. As part of the diaspora, we must be mindful not to complain too much because we were fortunate enough to have the means to leave and adapt to life abroad. However, we also have family and friends who are still in Lebanon facing the challenging situation there, and we shouldn't feel guilty for saying that creating a balance when you are left unprepared is challenging.

ŞE: Thank you all for being here... Thank you Noel for being here.

NK: Thank you very much.

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